

Basic guide on patentability in natural-derived products for venom-based researchers.

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This document is compiled based on the workshop **“INTELLECTUAL PROPERTY IN RESEARCH ON NATURAL COMPOUNDS”** organised on 10th of June 2022 by EUVEN.

Talk 1: “IP in Biotechnology” by Dr Sebastian Tegethoff on behalf of the European IP Helpdesk

European IP Helpdesk: The European IP Helpdesk is a service managed by the European Innovation Council and SMEs Executive Agency (EISMEA), with policy guidance provided by the European Commission’s Directorate-General for Internal Market, Industry, Entrepreneurship and SMEs (DG Grow). It supports cross-border SME and research activities to manage, disseminate and valorise technologies and other Intellectual Property (IP) Rights and IP assets at an EU level. It offers a broad range of informative material, a Helpline service for direct IP support and on-site and online training. The European IP Helpdesk's main goal is to support IP capacity building along the full scale of IP practices: from awareness to strategic use and successful exploitation. This strengthening of IP competencies focuses on EU SMEs, participants and candidates in EU-funded projects, and EU innovation stakeholders for an increased translation of IP into the EU innovation ecosystem. The European IP Helpdesk assists in matters related to personal support on a specific IP issue, information about the latest developments in the world of IP and Innovation in Europe and/or a training session on IP.

Expert Bio: Dr Sebastian Tegethoff (Fortmann Tegethoff Patent & lawyers Intellectual Property Attorneys). Dr. Tegethoff develops IP strategies for research institutes as well as for companies from start-

ups to medium-sized. Dr. Tegethoff combines biological and medical issues with technical approaches. He advises med, biotech, and pharmaceutical companies. He is approved before German, Austrian, European and Swiss patents and trademark authorities.

Key points: The field of biotechnology is regarded as one of the most innovative fields in terms of developing future applications. The protection of biotech inventions by appropriate Intellectual Property Rights is extremely important due to the close link between such innovations and the development of a product. Thus, “Patent Off” for instance has to be avoided. This IP training session gave an overview about relevant IP rights, the context of IP in product development, specifics of IP in biotech as well as the development and management of an IP portfolio.

Intellectual property (IP) is related to a mind creation, or a technical innovation used in commerce. Therefore, there is a need for a strategy involving IP, portfolio, or trademarks. An IP strategy covers basic, innovative, or proof of concept research results and publication should be avoided prior to IP filing. IP is a dynamic process and thus, should be adjusted as the product develops and new applications may be filed.

IP is validity for 20 years, but the product development could take up to 10 years. An IP application is surrounded by claims, defining the matter for which protection is applied. Consequently, claims should be clear and concise with supporting descriptions. Claims contain technical features that have an advantage and distinguish the current invention from prior art (unity of invention) with technical effects. In the application, it is detailed all embodiments and combinations of features that highlight their advantages. A patent should be filed based on its novelty or “not obviousness”, distinct technical features, and superiority towards existing inventions to be granted.

Patent protection could cover a compound/composition of matter, their process, the method of treating a disease (first time or second medical use) OR the use of compound/composition (medical use is not allowed in USA). In Europe, claims could be made for products or composition (sequence) but not for treatments (*i.e.*, maintain or restore health, physical integrity or wellbeing of a human or animal). Of note, there are different levels of patent protection.

A patent where claims combine various technical features should be avoided because they might not clearly convey their relevance and significance to the patent examiner and therefore may not be granted. Technical features should be clear & specific, showcasing the advantages of the proposed innovation. Examples (experiments) should be provided to support such claims. In addition, prior art such as relevant publications should be disclosed and critically discussed. This is an opportunity for the applicant to distinguish their invention from prior art knowledge in the field. The applicant should focus on interpreting accurately their findings without unsupportive claims or speculations. It is imperative that a patent is first filed and then being disclosed to the public (*e.g.*, conferences or publications).

Examples of filing an application.

Classic. Filing for a national patent in the country of residency. The application can be in the country's language. For example, in German, English, Spanish *etc.* It is cost effective as it ranges between 300 and 500 €. However, it does not provide coverage outside the country of submission.

Classic Luxury. Filing for a European patent via the European Patent Office. The application can be written in German, English or French and conveys EU protection in a geographical context, including Luxembourg, Sweden, Finland, and many other countries. The cost is higher than the classic application and of approx. 1500 €.

Exotic. If one of the inventors of the patent is a US citizen, then it is advisable to file in the United States Patent & Trademark Office. The language is English, and the fees are around 280US\$. In that case, no research report is provided.

Aim of filing for a patent

1. Get invention published to allow freedom to operate OR
2. Grant of a patent via enforceable IP rights

In the first case, you can apply in UK with a fee of 150£, which subsequent filing is possible whether search report is positive.

However, for granted IP applications, requirements include quality search report and cited prior art, flexibility with amendment claims, speed up grant procedure, reduced cost, as well as high quality.

National to European Application

Several European countries use the European Patent Office as the Search Authority for a national patent application. Hence, the applicant acquires a European-Style search report, which allows to identify relevant prior art and adapt the claims accordingly and/or provide description to the European requirements within the first year after filing the priority application. The applicant is familiarised to the European examination procedure. Of note, whether a patent lawyer conducts a European search report via the patent office the fee could be national, but the search is conducted via the EU patent office and therefore would cover EU patents. Subsequently, when the applicant applies to the European Patent Office, the latter has already seen the application. Indeed, whether EPO conducts the national search authority, frequently the same examiner will oversee assessing the later European application. The patent search will not be repeated, and part of the paid national fees may be credited in the EU search. The advantage of this strategy is that it has a broader degree of freedom for revision in comparison to an EU filed application.

Example Luxembourg. The application is in French, German, or English. In the case of the latter, only the claims will be translated, and the cost is approx. 490€.

IP strategy

A patent search covers:

- Search report on patentability
- Insights on relevant prior art & freedom to operate
- The landscape of competitors

Aspects to consider deriving from the search report.

Carefully analyze the results. If the outcomes of filing for a provisional patent are negative, it might be advisable for the authors to withdraw/retract the application and re-assess their further steps (*e.g.*, new first filing) while proceed with sufficient and new data. If the reviewers provide a positive assessment, the

inventors have 12 months to address objections in the first search report and to file a subsequent, amended application.

Regardless of the patent an inventor chooses to file, it is important to have it published for the freedom to operate.

Alternative to patenting applications

Inventors that do not wish to have their data published; they may then convey their invention as a trade secret. In that case, the company must define the **trade secret**. “Trade secret” is an information that is secret in the sense that is not as a body or in the precise configuration of its components generally known among or readily accessible to persons within the network that normally deal with this kind of information. It has a commercial value because it is a secret and has been a subject to reasonable steps by the person lawfully in control of the information to be kept as such. This information is not publicly known and can be controlled. The holder of a trade secret (natural or legal person) is aware of its significance (to protect it) and does not belong to the public. Parties holding this information could be the inventor, the attorney, the patent office and funding bodies. Other parties having access to this information could belong to a consortium, CRO or collaborating companies/academia. The owner of the trade uses agreements to regulate the generated information. For example, Non-disclosure Agreements (NDA) OR Collaborative Agreements. In those agreements, regulations regarding known secrets (background) and future knowledge based on secrets (known information) are to be negotiated. Handling of trade secrets requires various levels of access, including data room with no computers or infrastructure for copies not to be made without NDA. Patent protection cannot be sought on a trade secret. The trade secret could be prepared in a similar way to a patent. However, the information containing would be a secret and not available to the public. Withdrawing a pending patent application is feasible when converted to a trade secret. However, to define a trade secret a repaired patent applications could be used as Annex, exploring the subject matter of the trade secret. EU has a directive concerning the protection of undisclosed know-how and business information (Directive EU2016/943).

Questions & Answers

Q: Is it advisable to file in additional than EU countries and why is that?

A: An EU patent can be further extended to speed up the protection in other countries. The inventors might decide to file in additional than EU countries (e.g., USA, China, Japan, Australia, or Singapore) based

on their interest to sell or manufacture their product. Therefore, they might choose to file their application in multiple countries for a wider IP coverage.

Q: Do attorneys use various patent search engines other than Europeans?

A: When filing for an EU patent the attorney uses various search engines to gain a complete picture of the relevant prior art.

Q: How important is the filing date of an application & what protection provides towards other similar applications filed at the same time?

A: The filing date is important for competitors. There is an 18-month grace period when context of patents is not available. Therefore, there are cases of similar patents that they have been submitted at approximately the same time.

Talk 2: "Introduction on patentability in academia"

Eskisehir Osmangazi University is a state university established in Eskişehir in 1993 but the year 1970, when Eskişehir State Engineering Architecture Academy (EDMMA) was founded, is used as the "foundation year" with a decision of Senate. Eskişehir Osmangazi University is a strong and long-established university with more than 50 years of scientific experience. The University continues to produce knowledge with 12 Faculties, 2 Schools, 5 Vocational Schools, 4 Institutes and 35 Application and Research Center, more than 30,000 students and progressing steadily towards modern science. The Technology Transfer Office (ETTOM) of the university, provides support to both academia and private sector organizations in R&D and innovation activities in Eskişehir and its periphery. It also provides the necessary infrastructure and mentorship to entrepreneurs in technology-based entrepreneurship activities. They work with the slogan "From Academy to Economy" to increase the commercialization potential of knowledge.

Expert Bio: Dr. Şahin Coşkun is the head of Technology Transfer Office in ETTOM and Assistant Professor at Department of Metallurgical and Materials Engineering at Eskişehir Osmangazi University. His expertise is on nanomaterials and their optoelectronic applications. Dr. Şahin Coşkun has 7 patents applications and 4 of them are granted. He is also co-founder and has an academic spin-off company in order to commercialize their patents.

Key points: This talk provides an overview about general patentability in biotechnology from a university perspective. **A patent is an exclusive right granted for an invention or a process that provides a new**

application or a new technical solution to a problem. A patent provides the limited monopoly right by the state to the inventor and prevents other parties to benefit -from the invention- without permission. Important criteria for patentability are:

Novelty (an invention not known previously to the public), non-obviousness (inventive step not obvious to a person with ordinary skill in the prior art), **industrial application** in the context of utility, susceptibility or enabling (sufficient description of the invention for others to practice).

Prior to filing a patent application, inventors obtain patentability opinion from a patent agent/attorney whether their invention meets the conditions of patentability. The application is subject to an official examination performed by a patent examiner. A patent should meet all relevant legal conditions to be granted. For example, the invention to be novel or not obvious from prior art and to be sustainable for industry applications. A “not-obvious” invention could not be predicted using ordinary skills by someone familiar to the art. The claiming invention should be distinct and/or to enhances the scientific knowldege of prior art. **Prior art** could be classified as other patents, printed applications, publications, conference presentations, talks, blogs, website posts, videos, patents or anykind of disclosure in the field of invention before the effective filing date, which suggest or elute (part) or the whole invention.

What can be patented:

- A new (product, compound, method, property, substance, machine, a technique)
- Pharmaceutical compositions
- Dosing regimes
- A new manufacturing process or product development
- A composition of a matter.
- An aparatus or a new technology
- A technological application
- A drug delivery system
- Recombinant gene products
- Research tools
- Monoclonal antibodies
- Transgenic animals & plants

- Synergistic properties resulting from a mixture of compounds with distinct properties from one to another

What cannot be patented:

- Scientific principles or super conductance phenomena (*e.g.*, Newton's laws of gravity)
- A claim that a machine can perform more than 100% efficiency
- The discovery of principles or scientific formulation of abstract theories involving living or nonliving things in nature
- A commercial exploitation of material(s) in grounds of morality in humans, animals, plants, or environment (*e.g.*, gambling machines or housebreaking devices)
- Plants, animals (whole or parts), seeds, species, biological procedures of products
- Biological warfare materials or devices
- Terminator gene technology
- Embryonic stem cells
- A substance resulting from a mixture

Of note, methods of Agriculture or Horticulture cannot be patent but can be protected as claims in some countries.

It should be differentiated that the discovery adds to the human knowledge by disclosing something not seen before. However, an invention, is a human knowledge by suggesting an action resulting in a new product, new machine, or process/application.

In order a patent to be granted it must meet the requirements set by the patent examiner. Hence, the inventor prior of filing for an application they should consult the appropriate agencies or attorneys to ensure their claims are patentable. The confidentiality prior to filing for a patent is imperative. Therefore, academics should receive appropriate consultation (*e.g.*, Transfer Knowledge Offices) and whether share materials or exchange information with other institutes or companies to have in place Non-Disclosure Agreements (NDA) or Material Transfer Agreements (MTA). Useful free patent searching tools are Google Patents, ESPACENET, patsnap USPTO, PQAI, Patentscope by WIPO or Lens.org, Innography *etc.*

Questions & Answers

Q: Can you patent a purified protein (*e.g.*, from an animal venom)?

A: It might be easier to patent a modified version of the protein.

Talk 3: “Filing an academic patent”

The National Institute of Chemistry in Slovenia is a scientifically excellent, established and breakthrough research institution in Europe. It is specialized in chemistry and related disciplines with background in biotechnology, among other fields. It successfully transfers knowledge to the industrial environment, thus supporting the placement of science in societal development in the long run.

Expert Bio: **Dr. Vojka Žunič** is heading the Knowledge Transfer Office at the National Institute of Chemistry, Slovenia. Her areas of expertise include the protection and commercialization of intellectual property, created at the Institute. She is responsible for the management of the Institute's policy in the field of knowledge and technology transfer. She is a member of the Association of Technology Transfer Professionals Slovenia and active in the national and international innovation ecosystem. She started her career as a young researcher at the Advanced Materials Department of the Jožef Stefan Institute and received her PhD in Nanoscience and Nanotechnology from the Jožef Stefan International Postgraduate School. During this period, she was involved in research and development of advanced materials for self-cleaning and antibacterial purposes, and worked on applied projects with economy. She continued her career in the pharmaceutical industry at Lek a Sandoz Company (Novartis International AG), where she was involved in the development of the biopharmaceutical product and participated in a number of nationally and culturally diverse project teams and collaborated with public research institutions.

Key points: The Technology Transfer Office (TTO) provides support to IP protection & commercialization, Networking with companies & concluding agreements as well as advice on spin-out companies. The IP process starts with a new discovery by researchers. The researcher creates results that they believe can be patented. Therefore, they notify the TTO of the institute to discuss their data and whether they meet the patentability requirements. The TTO assesses their invention disclosure by performing a prior art and market search and provide their opinion on patentability & commercialisation. The TTO then files a priority patent application at the national patent office. If the patent application meets the legislative criteria, the patent is granted, and the application is made public after the 18 months of filing. During that

time other parties are excluded from commercialising the invention. Of note, the owner of a patent is also not eligible to commercialise their invention unless they have been granted the freedom to operate. This means that it is confirmed that other patents on the same invention are not active. In that case, the inventor has a monopoly of their invention for 20 years, starting from the priority date of the application. Patent is a negative right that excludes others from commercial exploitation of your invention and thus, provides a local monopoly.

Three main requirement steps for filing a patent.

1. The novelty, which translates to no (partial or whole) previous disclosure available
2. The inventive step, where experts of your field cannot, based on the prior art, put together the invention
3. The potential industrial application or added value.

Applicant can be an individual person or a legal entity, where the inventor is employed. The inventor has moral rights (inventorship) but the applicant gains material rights to patent (ownership). The inventor is recommended to consult with a patent attorney and the TTO of their entity before filing for a patent application. In cases of joint ownership of an invention and prior to filing a patent, it should be defined the shares of individual inventors according to their contribution. In such cases, relevant parties should sign a joined ownership agreement to define rights related to invention. Specifically:

- Rights related to the invention
- Ownership proportion related to achieved results
- Investment resources related to human expertise, materials, infrastructure
- Percentage of shares
- Protection of results
- Decisions to be taken
- Administrative role in filing a patent
- Distribution of expenses based on % of ownership agreement
- Exploitation and commercialisation of the invention
- License agreements
- Commercialization income

- % of ownership

All the above can be negotiated by mutual understanding.

The inventor is legally obliged to disclose their results to their perspective employee, who can decide whether they will file a patent or publish a scientific article. Some benefits of having a granted patent might involve an additional income for the inventors and academic prestige. The inventors could first file for a priority application to their National Patent Office. An application filed to the National Patent Office is not examined for prior art or review of the claims, but only if it complies to the national legislations. After 9 years of the national filing of the application, the proof of full patent examination should be submitted, usually obtained via the EU patent office and the patent could be granted and valid for 20 years from the initial date of application. Annual fees should be paid for maintaining the validity of the patent.

Procedure and timeline (national and EPO)

The applicant submits an “application of invention”. The University/Institute prepares the patent application. It files then the national application (SIPO). This process takes approximately 3 months. The inventor is granted a national patent and can then publish their research. After 18 months, the application is made publicly available. The inventor has then 9 years to obtain the proof of complete examination and in total has protection for 20 years before the patent expires. In some cases, the entity decides to file for a European patent Application (EPO) a year (12 months – 1 day) after the filing of the national patent application. In the case of EPO application, they first file a priority application in Luxembourg to follow EU routes for patentability, including patent search. This process lasts approximately one year (~12 months) and provides the applicant time to perform additional experiments to validate their invention. Upon full examination of the application by EU patent office, the European patent is granted. The process can take up to three years. The applicant may then decide in which countries to validate their patent based on commercialization, protection from competitors, manufacturing interests, and market location.

Questions & Answers

Q: How important is for the portfolio of a university to have filed patents?

A: It is very important because it reflects scientific excellency. However, it can be a financial burden; thus, only selected applications are filed as patents, other become trade secret, or be published.

Talk 4: “Licensing an academic patent”

The University of Cadiz (UCA) was founded in 1979. It has nine main research areas and seven Research Institutes, which integrate the research excellence of the Institution as well as the specialized scientific infrastructure. UCA leads the "CAMPUS DE EXCELENCIA INTERNACIONAL DEL MAR" (CEIMAR), a strategic alliance of universities, research centres, science and technology parks and innovative companies of the South of Spain, Portugal and the North of Morocco and the European University of the Seas one of the 17 selected transnational alliances in the first call of European Universities Initiative.

Expert Bio: Dr. Fernando Merello Luna is the Knowledge Transfer Office Delegation Manager at University of Cadiz. He holds a MSc in Analytical Chemistry & MSc in Applied Economy. He is also the Head of Laboratory and Quality Control at PROMSA (Italcementi Group), Chemist at Technical Department of Terry Wines and Spirits, Osborne Fellowship for research in Sherry wines. He has 25 years of experience in knowledge transfer management and is participant in several projects at regional (10), national (11) and international (9) level in the field of technology transfer.

Key points: Commercialization showcases a formal relationship between universities and companies, many times to manage R&D contracts. Hence, universities have established commercialization protocols. In this talk, it was highlighted the significance of IP for universities to engage with companies and to form various agreements. There are two major activities to license. Finding a company interested in your IP and agreeing on terms of licensing. Important documents in the process are as follows.

- NDA (Non-Disclosure Agreement) that allows freedom of information exchange.
- MTA (Material Transfer Agreement) for sharing materials without losing control of possession and use (research collaborations for public or private), testing, patent filings, etc.
- OLA Option License Agreement. To grant temporary right (IP or bio property) to obtain longer-term right such as the exclusion right to test, license or buy.

Basics of licensing. A license is a contract where the holder of an IP (licensor) grants permission for the use of its intellectual property to another person (licensee), within limits sets by the provisions of the contract. Thus, license agreements are used with provisions and disclosures. Key terms to define are commencement, duration & termination. In addition, the identification of the IP (excluded IP & technological developments), type of licensing: exclusive or non-exclusive, purpose, geographical scope

& coverage, field of use, right to sublicense (license for selling or sub selling *etc.*). It is an opportunity for universities not to limit their exploration potential. In addition, they provide to a company the right to license their invention with conditions while the researchers maintain the right to continue using their technology for research purposes. Furthermore, the payment provisions are clarified. For example, upfront payments (recoupable or not against royalties), stage payments, installments or milestones and royalties (net sales value or per service provided). Option license agreements could provide a route of escape to companies and recovery of their money in case the innovation cannot be substantially developed.

Discussions with companies is a critical assessment of the technology as well as on the identification of any weaknesses that might forbid its competitiveness in the market. In the experience of UCA, when a university engages with various companies to receive feedback on the innovation that could contribute to its improvement and licensing, of all the companies approached, 90% ignores the invitation, 8% provides constructive feedback and 2-3% engages to licensing discussions.

Talk 5: “Licensing and academic collaborations: the private company point of view”

LATOXAN: Is a company involved in production of venoms, fractions and molecules extracted from venoms, trading of plant extracts with applications in cosmetics, feed, and agriculture.

Expert Bio: Dr. Harold de Pomyers is a Doctor in Veterinary Medicine, INSEAD MBA with 30 years in scientific and marketing positions in Life Sciences businesses including pharmaceutical products, Veterinary feed and medicinal products, food supplements. He is the major shareholder and CEO of LATOXAN.

Key points: In this talk, the perspective of a company about their interest to form academic collaborations was presented. A company collaborates with universities to acquire access to scientific knowledge and prior art, state-of-the art infrastructure, lab space and skills via qualified personnel. In addition, the company is eligible for governmental and other financial incentives, including substitutions. In such collaborations (*e.g.*, research collaboration conventions) many parties may be involved. For example, the company, various universities and/or hospitals or other public institutions. Therefore, it is imperative the appropriate agreements to be formed prior to the commencement of a project. Such agreements define

the theme & extend of research, resources, duration of collaboration, sharing ownership in proportion to financial and intellectual contribution as well as terms & domain of use of results.

Licensing process: A university that owns 70% of the IP is responsible for licensing the innovation. License occurs directly or via Technology Transfer Acceleration Companies (*e.g.*, in France there are SATTs) or simplified stock companies owned by regional academic bodies (*e.g.*, Universities). SATT companies are usually sub licensed by universities for the exploitation of their findings to develop them further or bring their invention into the market. These companies have access to various expertise, skills, infrastructure, protects the IP, evaluate the invention and bring it directly into the market or by sub contracting. Results belong to academic institutions but are patented by SATT. Universities contract SATT via an Exclusive Sublicense Option on exploitation of results. Two types of contracts are mainly conducted with SATT. A maturation contract to bring the invention to the market, covering exploitation of the invention, the first stages of product and IP development, phototyping, validation of the proof of concept, market evaluation, legal and financial support. In exclusive sublicensed contracts, the domain of product exploitation is defined, the territory & duration. SATT can provide financial support for filing and maintaining the patent or via predetermined payment milestones in the form of royalties or by sub-contracting and/or related to the development of a drug, including preclinical regulation or clinical regulation (phase I, II and III) or first drug approval entry. That is characterization of the offer, economic model, markets, and time to market.

Licensing with SATT covers the royalties associated with sublicensing with the pharma. It is therefore imperative to negotiate domain, territory, time to exercise the option, financial conditions related to marketing and sales as well as ESL contract. The latter covers, financing the industrial property, down payments for direct exploitation. For example, predefined amounts of milestones payments (Entry to all clinical phases (I, II, III) and 1st approval. Financial conditions for the ESCL contract involve, royalties on income from sub-sublicenses, % on revenues, % varies with milestones, milestones as defined above. It is therefore imperative to define the financial conditions. The net income of the company (less expenses translate to less royalties to SATT), potential expected revenues from sub sublicensing to the Pharma. Validation points of the subsublicense, involve derisking (*e.g.*, stage of development, risk of failure at each developmental stage, value of sublicensing, payment terms, targeted market size and achievable share, market-associated risks, time to market, total cash flow expected from sales of the drug, potential shares,

expected drug sales and returned investments, targeted return on investment, among others. For this reason, a financial adviser should be employed.

Payment terms by the Pharma:

An overall percentage on sales to be negotiated and compared to overall royalties' percentage negotiated with SATT

Down payment. The bigger the better since development can be lengthy.

Royalties as reflected by milestones of important developmental processes, proportioned with the associated risk.

Questions & Answers

Q: What is the expected time frame for a drug to reach the market?

A: It depends on the field of innovation. For example in the therapeutic field, it is still approximately 10 years

Q: Are there any new venom-derived drugs coming into the market?

A: Yes, related to antibiotics, pain, and cancer.

Q: What are the criteria to select a SATT company? (Manuel Fernandez-Rojo)

A: This is usually based on the region a university belongs to.

Q: How essential is to have a patent lawyer in the product development? (Manuel Fernandez-Rojo)

A: It is important, if you can afford it financially. Otherwise, the most essential is to have a financial adviser with knowledge about pharma industry to help you calculate the value of sublicensing that you offer (to the pharma).

Talk 6: "From research to patenting: the academic point of view"

The **University of Copenhagen** is a public research university in Copenhagen, Denmark. Founded in 1479, the University of Copenhagen is the second-oldest university in Scandinavia after Uppsala University and ranks as one of the top universities in the Nordic countries and Europe.

Expert Bio: Associate Prof Helena Safavi at the Department of Biomedical Sciences, University of Copenhagen and Associate Prof at the Department of Biochemistry, University of Utah. She did her master's in biology at the University of Cologne, Germany, her PhD in Biochemistry and Molecular Biology at the University of Melbourne in Australia and her postdoctoral studies in the USA and Denmark. Her

research focuses on the biomedical applications of marine venoms. Assoc/Prof. Safavi is an inventor on three patents that were filed in the USA and/or Australia (one of which has been licensed). She is also co-founder of a small biotech company in the USA.

Key points: Assoc/Prof. Safavi briefly introduced the topic of her field, which is insulin peptides derived from cone snails and their therapeutic advantage in relation to their human counterparts. Her first USA filed patent was on conesnail insulin peptides and her consequent second and third patent on analogues. Dr. Safavi emphasized the challenge of finding the balance between IP protection and development and research priorities (publications, conference presentations, theses, and grant applications).

To DO:

Contact the Technology Transfer Office (TTO) of your university when you identify that your data might have commercialization potential. A challenge might be for the researcher to convince the TTO advisor of the potential commercial value of their invention because filing a patent is costly. However, if the TTO is convinced, they will then ask you to complete an invention disclosure to clarify the invention and its significance. During this time, the inventor will be in close contact with the TTO until the provisional patent is filed. This is because the scientist should prepare all relevant information related to the invention (*e.g.*, sequences, activity data, etc.). Of importance, if other parties are involved in the research, then they need to be contacted. Hence, ideally all the appropriate collaborative agreements should be in place (*e.g.*, CDAs, MTAs) before sharing data or material. It is also important that IP protection is in place before data are shared publicly. In addition, if you have received funding for the research, you must be aware of any IP conditions required by the funding agencies.

To proceed with IP:

The invention should be novel (prior art and obviousness) based on existing knowledge or information publicly available. Of note, natural products are difficult to protect in USA. Thus, modifications should be made to the original natural compound. Another important step is to prepare a strategy for patentability, including when to submit the patent application. A filed provisional patent gives you a priority date that protects you from other similar patents that might be filed afterwards. You are then allowed to share information and publish your invention BUT you should disclose the patent and therefore, reveal any potential conflict of interest. It is also recommended to contact your TTO prior to any publication or other disseminations (thesis, conference presentations *etc.*) to make sure the data are indeed protected. After

filing the provisional patent, you have approximately one year to collect more data to support your claims and convince the patent examiners to grant the patent. A drug patent typically expires after 20 years which gives just enough time for the university to license the product and the company to develop it further to -hopefully- reach the market well in time before the patent expires. Because of the high costs of developing a drug lead into a therapeutic, you need to find a licensing partner or get your own startup company. In some European countries, for example in Denmark, researchers who build a startup based on their invention can license their own patent. The licensing conditions typically need to be negotiated with the host university. Either way, preclinical studies (IND/CTA-enabling stage) and clinical trials are extremely expensive and lengthy.

DON'Ts:

- Share your data with a third party without IP protection or the appropriate agreements (e.g., MTAs/NDAs).
- File a patent too early or too late.
- Give up on your invention (get support), you might need to pitch your case to your TTO and receive support from senior colleagues.
- Do not get too attached to your own invention because if patented, you will assign all your rights to the university and licensing partner. Of importance, some funding agencies also have rights to your invention.

Questions & Answers

Q: Does a company care if you publish after you file for a patent? Does this limit their interest to license it?

A: Most of the time not, a requirement is that the invention is protected to be developed and reach the market.

Talk 6 by Dr. Esperanza Rivera de Torre

The Technical University of Denmark (DTU) is recognized internationally as a leading university in the areas of the technical and the natural sciences, renowned for its business-oriented approach, and focus on sustainability.

Expert Bio: Dr. Rivera de Torre is an early career, postdoctoral researcher in the Tropical Pharmacology Laboratory at DTU Bioengineering headed by Prof. Andreas H. Laustsen. Esperanza did her thesis in the Biochemistry and Molecular Biology department of the Chemistry Faculty at the Complutense University of Madrid under the supervision of Prof. Álvaro Martínez del Pozo. She studied the biophysical aspects of the toxin mechanism of pore-forming proteins from sea anemone and black widow spider venom. Dr. Rivera de Torre combined her research with multiple science outreach activities, including popular science talks like the TEDx Talk “Big Data and Venomics.” She moved to Denmark in 2020 to work on next generation antivenom development based on human monoclonal antibodies. Particularly, she is developing methods for the discovery of broadly neutralizing antibodies to treat spider bites and scorpion stings.

Key points: The speaker is working on effective and long lasting neutralising antibodies (from spiders and scorpions) for envenomated victims in undeveloping countries, which claims millions of lives every year. Patenting an antibody can be challenging as you cannot patent the target of an antibody since there are companies who can be serviced for that. You cannot also patent “something” that binds to “something”. You can though patent the specific properties for the binding and how these properties have beneficial effects (*e.g.*, diminish side effects/toxicity). You can also patent the exact region of binding (complementarity determining regions -CDRs).

In Denmark, there is a strong supportive network in all steps of commercialisation. In fact, there is a dedicated department on innovation & creation of spin up companies from the university (DTU Skylab). Academics in Denmark are legally bound by their contracts to file for an invention notification if their data could be commercialised. However, if the Business Development Unit refrains from filing a patent and the inventor proceeds with their own expenses, the Danish university legally receives a percentage from the royalties. After filing for a patent priority application, the rights of the invention are transferred to the university. Caution should be exercised by the Principal Investigators in involving students, who need to publish their data to obtain their degree. To evaluate the maturity of invention we use the KTH innovation Rediness Level (IRL) , which assesses according to six different dimensions:

- Team Readiness Level: build, develop & align team
- Technology Readiness Level: develop & test technology
- IPR Readiness Level: explore and develop suitable IP protection

- Customer Readiness Level: confirm market need and interest
- Business Readiness Level: confirm business model and financial potential
- Funding Readiness : Prepare for investment and secure funding

DTU Skylab: Danish Universities provide grants to cover the various stages of patentability. If a researcher requires funding to collect preliminary data for a grant application or an idea (Pre-project), they can then apply for a super-fast track grant of approximately €20k. This grant is normally for a year and is an open call. In addition, there is the proof-of-concept grant (Project), which is more competitive for €65k. Another type of grant is the Inno Explorer Grant (Company) of 200k. Afterwards innovators interested in startups could apply for venture capital (e.g., novo nordisk fonden). There is also other specific funding for patenting, pioneer Innovator Grant (12 months, 130K), spin up grants, BII (BioInnovation Institute) OR ERC Proof of Concept (European level competition and very competitive with restrictions in eligibility). Denmark is suited for translating science from the lab to society.

In Denmark, scientists are supported financially to translate their innovation and file for a patent. Assoc/Prof. Helena Safavi highlighted that protecting electronic labnote books is not a necessary measure to protect the intellectual property, since the provisional filing date is the most important aspect of protection.

In Denmark, scientists are supported financially to translate their innovation and file for a patent. However, they need to have electronic lab books, which are password protected. Assoc/Prof. Helena Safavi highlighted that this is not valid anymore but the provisional filing date is the most important aspect of protection.

Q& A Session (Moderator: Dr. Maria Ikonomopoulou)

Key points: This was an interactive session among the moderator, speakers, and participants. Below are questions that were raised and comments that were addressed by the speakers.

The moderator enquired whether universities with the exemption of Denmark are less inclined to file a patent in comparison to their non-European counterparts.

Dr. Tegethoff confirmed that this is his impression and there should be more patents/companies from ECRs in Europe.

Moderator: Is the not “non-obvious” the main reason why a patent is failed?

Dr. Tegethoff: Inventors do not understand when their invention is not “non-obvious” therefore the patent lawyers should be clear from the beginning that their invention may not be patentable.

Dr Helena Safavi: Patent attorneys use a different language than scientists. It is important that the scientists include the “good” and the “bad” data, including all positive and negative controls. For example, analogues that are active or non-active should be included, not just the active ones.

Moderator: Helena, you had a company, can you please tell us about your experience in filing a patent that was licensed by your company?

Dr Helena Safavi: As you know when you patent, you assign the rights to your university, which later decides to whom they will license your invention. Usually, they give preference to the inventor. If the inventors do not have a start-up company, the university approaches other companies. If you license your own IP, the university usually gives you better conditions than it may give to other companies.

Dr Violette Aude: Can you please explain the cost of maintenance of a patent?

Dr. Tegethoff: The cost of maintenance starts in the third year and increases every year. For pharma companies a patent lasts 20 years while mechanical patents lasts 11-13 years. You also pay associated fees to parties involved in the process (e.g., patent lawyers).

Dr Violette Aude: Was it complicated (Helena Safavi) to file a patent for a natural sequence (insulin)?

Dr Helena Safavi: Yes, it is easier if you do at least one modification to the natural sequence

Dr Manuel Fernandez Rojo: Can you submit a paper or prepare a paper for publication prior to filing for a patent?

Dr Esperanza Rivera de Torre: Yes, if you have NDA or MTAs with your collaborators with whom you share the paper. You share more freely this information. You ensure also that the paper is not published (is under embargo) until you have filed for a provisional patent and have a registered date. You can submit for reviewing but you have to disclose that it cannot be published until you have the priority date. Another issue might be if your reviewers are your competitors and if they are aware of your invention, they might file a patent first.

Dr Helena Safavi: It is imperative that your publication preparation does not threaten your patent application. You should also be aware that when you apply for funding for your invention, the funding body does not publish your abstract or progress report without the inventor's knowledge and thus, jeopardises your patent filing. Therefore, it is important to have an early priority date on your patent prior to any publication.

Moderator: I would like to ask the university representatives whether they encourage scientists to be actively involved to engage with companies for licensing their invention.

Dr. Vojka Žunič: The National University of Slovenia encourages scientists to be actively involved and engage directly with companies because they have a deep knowledge on market and the companies that they might be interested in licensing their invention.

Dr. Şahin Coşkun: The applicant of an IP is the university, and they own all rights. Therefore, it is essential to have discussions and make agreements based on mutual understanding. This approach will be mutually beneficial for the commercialization of the product and its further development, which is essential.

Moderator: If a scientist files a patent in their institute and the following year they move to another institute, can they transfer the IP rights?

Dr. Şahin Coşkun: The applicant of an IP is the university of the inventor, and they own all rights. Therefore, it is essential to have discussions and make agreements based on mutual understanding. It will be mutually beneficial for the commercialization of the product and its further development, which is essential.

Moderator: The conclusion is researchers to have great negotiation skills.

Chat question (Margot, UK): How important is for filing a patent to be proficient in English. Will language have an impact in the review process of the IP application?

Dr Sebastian Tegethoff: It is easier for academics to write in English because of the learned terminology and the fact that the official language for science is English. However, there is the option for scientist to write in their own language if they file for a national patent.

Moderator: What does the industry looking for to form collaborations with academia.

Dr Harold de Pomier: When we want to improve a product or need access to scientific journals it is desirable to have a collaboration with the university because they can provide such access. They have

infrastructure and access to specialise equipment or databases for paper. In that case, we will pay for the services of the university. If there are new opportunities for the company based on current market, we have simple collaborations with academia. For example, to develop a simple protocol not necessarily for patenting or licensing.

Moderator: I believe that now companies depend more on universities to perform experiments on their behalf. What is the opinion of the industry representatives?

Dr Violette Aude: It depends on the opportunity. For example, many times industry might have PhD projects with academia and share basic knowledge. Other times, we have deeper collaborations with universities to have access to high analytical technology and equipment (state-of-the-art).

Dr Harold de Pomier: This is important for small companies that have no means to highly equipped lab and such collaborations are cost effective.

Chat question (Alex): Is a bioactive compound/extract from a marine organism subject to patentability?

Moderator: It might be easier to make modification(s) as we have heard from the previous talks.

Dr Harold de Pomier: You cannot patent a product derived directly from Nature. What pharma/industry does is optimise/modify for better efficacy and lower toxicity.

Dr Sebastian Tegethoff: Your extract compound is your starting point.

Moderator: How important is for a company the toxicity of a compound.

Dr Sebastian Tegethoff: Maybe not at the beginning when you file the patent but later on the company and later the drug regulatory bodies want to ensure that toxicity will not be an issue to bring a product in the market.

Moderator: Closing remarks and giving thanks to speakers and audience for their participation to the workshop.

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